

Tsallis Entropy Directly From a Maximization of Entropy Equation with an Sum over i $e^{-i/T} f(i)^q$ power q Constraint Part 2

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In Part I, we argued that one could obtain the functional form of Tsallis entropy in terms of $f(i)$ and q based on a physical constraint $\sum_i e^{-i/T} f(i)^q$ with $\sum_i f(i)=1$, together with the statement that $q=1$ should lead to Shannon's entropy. In other words, we argued that Tsallis entropy emerges in a very natural and physical manner. In particular, it is the probability $f(i)^q$, based on a product of the probability $f(i)$ which creates Tsallis entropy and both of these probabilities are physical as we argued in Part I. As an example, $f(i)$ is the probability that a sunflower seed is not eaten by a bird in a day (a bird being subject to a diurnal cycle) while a sunflower requires q days to germinate on average, but is almost entirely guaranteed to germinate if not eaten. Thus, information $e^{-i/T}$ is already contained in $f(i)$, but $f(i)^q$ is required to create averages using $e^{-i/T}$. This is how the Tsallis case differs from the usual Shannon one, we argue.

Here we consider the structure of the maximization of entropy subject to constraints in more detail. If $q=1$ yields Shannon's entropy, we argue that this is more than a mathematical transformation statement. Shannon's entropy is associated with Maxwell-Boltzmann physics. In other words, the form $f(i) \ln(f(i))$ such that $\ln(f(i)) = -e^{-i/T}$ so that the constraint is matched is a general condition that should hold for $f(i)^q$ as the probability, but now one requires a $\ln q$ function which is the inverse of $f(i)$ to obtain information. The key points then are that information, $-e^{-i/T}$, is obtained directly from $f(i)$ through $\ln q(f(i)) = -e^{-i/T}$, but averaging occurs through $f(i)^q$ because the actual production/distribution of $e^{-i/T}$ is linked with $f(i)^q$ as seen in the sunflower seed physical problem.

Even if one did not know Shannon's entropy, given $\sum_i S(f(i)) + A \sum_i e^{-i/T} f(i)^q + B \sum_i f(i)$ as an expression to be extremized, one may consider $S(f(i))$ as mimicking the main constraint $\sum_i e^{-i/T} f(i)^q$. In such a case, one would have: $\sum_i f(i)^q \ln q(f(i))$ such that $\ln q(f(i)) = -e^{-i/T}$. This simply means that f and $\ln q$ are inverse functions, but does not indicate exactly what either is. Then $f(i)^q \frac{d}{df} \ln q(f(i)) = \text{constant}$ ((1)). Entropy in the Shannon case is the average of an information function, and one assumes that this approach holds even for the $f(i)^q$ probability scenario. (We note that $f(i)^q$ need not be normalized to maximize entropy). In that case, one may see that ((1)) implies $\ln q(f)$ go as constant + $f(i)^{1-q}$. One may easily find S such that $q \rightarrow 1$ yields Shannon's entropy. Thus, we reiterate that physical constraint essentially governs the form of both Shannon's entropy and Tsallis entropy. It is assumed that both entropies are averages of an information $\ln(f)$ or $\ln q(f)$, with the information being $-e^{-i/T}$. Thus, Tsallis entropy is a natural extension of Shannon's entropy we argue, based on physical considerations, i.e. a physical meaningful probability $f(i)^q$.

Argument of Part I

In Part I, we argued that Tsallis entropy follows directly from maximizing an unknown entropy function subject to two constraints:

$$\sum_i f(e_i) = 1 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i f(e_i)^q = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((2b))$$

There is a distribution of total E (energy), but e_i results from $f(e_i)$ power q , which in turn results from $f(e_i)$. Thus, the relevant probability with respect to e_i is $f(e_i)$ power q (unnormalized at this point). The Tsallis picture follows almost directly from the Shannon picture with $f(e_i) \rightarrow f(e_i)$ power q for averaging, but $\ln(f(e_i)) \rightarrow \ln_q(f(e_i))$. As a result, there must be a very strong physical reason to use the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ power q .

We discussed a possible physical example related to a sunflower seed in detail in Part I. The main point is that $f(e_i)$ power q appears in nature as a physical probability linked with e_i , but depends on $f(e_i)$. As the probability linked with e_i , $f(e_i)$ power q should share the basic features of $f(e_i)$ in Shannon's entropy, we argue. It is not simply a mathematical convenience that $q \rightarrow 1$ yields Shannon's entropy.

In other words, in the Shannon formalism:

$$\text{Shannon's entropy} = \sum_i -f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) \quad ((3))$$

In the literature, it is stated that $\ln(f(e_i))$ represents information ($-e_i/t$) and that $f(e_i)$ is present because this information is being averaged. If these claims are taken seriously, then for the probability $f(e_i)$ power q , there should still be an information $\ln_q(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ because one has the same partitioning of energy e_i , albeit with a different probability. One does not need $f(e_i)$ power q to obtain the information $-e_i/T$, only for averaging purposes.

Thus, one should be able to write:

$$\text{Entropy Tsallis} = \sum_i f(e_i)^q \ln_q(f(e_i)) \quad ((4))$$

At this point, \ln_q is the inverse of $f(e_i)$, but both functions are completely unknown. There are, however, two conditions which must be met:

$$\ln_q(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T, \text{ the information} \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{and from the extremization process: } f(e_i)^q \frac{d}{df} \ln_q(f(e_i)) = \text{constant} \quad ((6))$$

We note that even if one did not know the form of Shannon's entropy one could write ((4)) with ((5)) and ((6)) as a math solution of the extremization problem. Linking to the Shannon's approach is good, however, we argue because in the $q=1$ case one obtains the Shannon picture and there should be some structural similarities based on the physics of the Shannon picture.

((6)) is readily solvable with:

$$\ln_q(f(e_i)) = \text{constant} + f(e_i)^{1-q} \quad ((7))$$

If one wishes to have $\ln_q \rightarrow \ln$ for $q \rightarrow 1$, then:

$$\ln_q(f) = \{1 - \sum_i f(e_i)^q\} / (1-q) \quad (8)$$

As an aside, if one wished to find Tsallis entropy using $\ln_{2q}(f(e_i)^q) = -e_i/T$ and

$f(e_i)^q \frac{d}{df} \ln_{2q}(f(e_i)^q)$, then $\{1 - f^q(-1 + 1/q)\} / (1-q)$. In order to test the limit $q \rightarrow 1$, one must use $f^q = f$ and so is back at the $\ln_q(f)$ expression. Given that one writes expressions in terms of $f(e_i)$, it seems that it is $f(e_i)$ that one wishes to find

The Constraint Seems to Completely Govern Shannon and Tsallis Entropy Extremization Processes

We suggest that the Tsallis and Shannon entropy extremization processes are almost entirely based on the constraint linked with the distribution of energy E_{total} . We note that in the microcanonical approach, which underlies Shannon entropy, one distributes E_{total} among N particles such that every distribution set $e_i - n_i$ times with $\sum e_i n_i = E_{total}$ and $\sum_i n_i = N$ carries the same weight. Thus, it is the distribution of E_{total} in an equi-weight approach which is the key to Shannon's entropy, hence the constraint: $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$. The basic idea is that $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_1+e_2)$ ((9)) unnormalized, suggesting a power law distribution. Then, $-e_i/T$ is due to a function $F(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. ((9)) shows that this function is \ln if $\ln(f(e_i))$ yields information related to the distributed entity energy.

In the Tsallis case, i.e. the sunflower which germinates with probability $f(e_i)^q$, there is still the same distribution entity energy as in the Shannon case. $f(e_i)^q$ could be denoted as $f_1(e_i)$, but it is $\ln_q(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. The main idea is that in terms of creating averages, $f_1(e_i) = f(e_i)^q$ is used, while the information e_i/T is already contained in $f(e_i)$ and one does not need to use $f_1(e_i)$ here.

One could then use $-f_1(e_i) \ln_q(f(e_i))$ as entropy which mimics the Shannon case and satisfies extremization of entropy as long as $f_1(e_i) \frac{d}{df} \ln_q(f(e_i)) = \text{constant}$. The derivative d/df is taken with respect to f and not $f(e_i)^q$, because $f(e_i)$ is the underlying probability given that q is a constant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for both Shannon's entropy and Tsallis entropy, the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ or $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)^q$ is the key to obtaining the math form of the entropy. In both cases, the entropy mimics the energy constraint with $f_1(e_i) \ln_q(f(e_i))$, where $\ln_q(f(e_i)) = e_i/T$. $f_1(e) = f(e)^q$ is the appropriate probability (unnormalized) to use to create averages, but information is already contained in $f(e_i)$ and so one uses $\ln_q(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. If one defines Shannon's entropy as: $\sum_i -f(e_i) \text{information}(f(e_i))$, where $\text{information}(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, then the same information applies to the Tsallis case, but $f(e_i) \rightarrow f(e_i)^q$. $\text{Information}(f(e_i))$ then means one needs the inverse function of f , which we call \ln_q . One has the added constraint that $f(e_i)^q \frac{d}{df} \ln_q(f(e_i)) = \text{constant}$, but then readily obtains a math expression for \ln_q whose constants may be immediately fixed in $\ln_q \rightarrow \ln$ for $q \rightarrow 1$.

